

Unit Cost Services of 1st Call

ELIXIRxNextGenIT National Open Access

This document reports the Unit Access Cost tables for the services provided under the ELIXIRxNextGenIT National Open Access (NOA) programme, funded by the European Union through NextGenerationEU.

The tables provide the unit cost values calculated for each service included in the NOA service catalogue and delivered by the ELIXIR-IT access providers involved in the call, namely CNR-IBIOM, the University of Bari Aldo Moro, and CNR-IBSBC.

The Unit Access Costs were calculated following the European Commission model for access to Research Infrastructures, adapted to the National Open Access framework of the ELIXIRxNextGenIT project. The calculation takes into account the eligible costs directly related to the provision of each service, including, where applicable, consumables, equipment maintenance, data storage, and indirect costs.

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CNR-IBIOM	TRS100	2
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Actual Unit Access Cost for the access offered under National Open Access (NOA)

Implementing Entity	CNR-IBIOM		
Service Provided	TRS100 - 82 RNAseq samples on flowcell S2		
Service Manager			
Number of accesses per year		25	
Instrumentation usage rate		90%	
Data storage volume (Tb)		11,00	
Cost of the instrumentations used to provide the service (IVA excluded)			
A. Direct eligible costs of providing access to the selected user groups, excluding personnel costs	costs of consumables and supplies specifically incurred for the provision of access to the selected users, in particular for carrying out their research work		Cost/year
	A1 - Consumables specifically used for service delivery (VAT excluded)		676.230,00 €
	A2 - Maintenance cost of all equipment used for service delivery [1]		- €
	A3 - Storage costs [2]		396,00 €
	VAT		148.857,72 €
	Total direct costs per year		825.483,72 €
B. Indirect eligible costs: 25% cost of consumables			Costo/anno
	B1- overhead costs [3]		169.057,50 €
	Total indirect costs per year		169.057,50 €
Actual Access Cost for the	Total cost		994.541,22 €
Unit Cost=(A+B)/(Number of Accesses *Number of samples per Access) [4]			€ 485,14

[1] Maintenance is calculated as 8% of the total cost of the equipment (VAT excluded). For the NOA/TNA covered by this call, the equipment is considered to be in use 90% of the total usage time.

[2] Costs related to the use of the Compute platform for storage. The calculation is EUR 3 per terabyte per month, i.e., EUR 36 per year/terabyte.

[3] Indirect costs for providing access to the installation equal to 25% of the direct costs (Costs of consumables specifically used for the service access)

[4] Unit Cost = Annual Total Cost [Direct Costs + Indirect Costs] / (Number of Accesses * Number of samples per access). The Unit Cost may vary depending on the service agreement signed by the parties and the technical report provided by the service manager. The maximum number of samples per access for this service is 24, and the unit cost may vary in relation to the sample saturation rate of the access.

Actual Unit Access Cost for the access offered under National Open Access (NOA)

Implementing Entity	CNR-IBIOM		
Service Provided	SRS20 - 108 sRNAseq samples on P3 NextSeq2000		
Service Manager			
Number of accesses per year		10	
Instrumentation usage rate		90%	
Data storage volume (Tb)		3,00	
Cost of the instrumentations used to provide the service (IVA excluded)			
A. Direct eligible costs of providing access to the selected user groups, excluding personnel costs	costs of consumables and supplies specifically incurred for the provision of access to the selected users, in particular for carrying out their research work		Cost/year
	A1 - Consumables specifically used for service delivery (VAT excluded)		162.000,00 €
	A2 - Maintenance cost of all equipment used for service delivery [1]		- €
	A3 - Storage costs [2]		108,00 €
	VAT		35.663,76 €
		Total direct costs per year	197.771,76 €
B. Indirect eligible costs: 25% cost of consumables			Costo/anno
	B1- overhead costs [3]		40.500,00 €
		Total indirect costs per year	40.500,00 €
Actual Access Cost for the	Total cost		238.271,76 €
Unit Cost=(A+B)/(Number of Accesses *Number of samples per Access) [4]			€ 220,62

[1] Maintenance is calculated as 8% of the total cost of the equipment (VAT excluded). For the NOA/TNA covered by this call, the equipment is considered to be in use 90% of the total usage time.

[2] Costs related to the use of the Compute platform for storage. The calculation is EUR 3 per terabyte per month, i. e., EUR 36 per year/terabyte.

[3] Indirect costs for providing access to the installation equal to 25% of the direct costs (Costs of consumables specifically used for the service access)

[4] Unit Cost = Annual Total Cost [Direct Costs + Indirect Costs] / (Number of Accesses * Number of samples per access). The Unit Cost may vary depending on the service agreement signed by the parties and the technical report provided by the service manager. The maximum number of samples per access for this service is 24, and the unit cost may vary in relation to the sample saturation rate of the access.

Actual Unit Access Cost for the access offered under National Open Access (NOA)

Implementing Entity	CNR-IBIOM		
Service Provided	MRS50 - 48 mRNAseq samples on P3 NextSeq2000		
Service Manager			
Number of accesses per year	10		
Instrumentation usage rate	90%		
Data storage volume (Tb)	4,00		
Cost of the instrumentations used to provide the service (IVA excluded)			
A. Direct eligible costs of providing access to the selected user groups, excluding personnel costs	costs of consumables and supplies specifically incurred for the provision of access to the selected users, in particular for carrying out their research work		Cost/year
	A1 - Consumables specifically used for service delivery (VAT excluded)		66.885,00 €
	A2 - Maintenance cost of all equipment used for service delivery [1]		- €
	A3 - Storage costs [2]		144,00 €
	VAT		14.746,38 €
	Total direct costs per year		81.775,38 €
B. Indirect eligible costs: 25% cost of consumables			Costo/anno
	B1- overhead costs [3]		16.721,25 €
	Total indirect costs per year		16.721,25 €
Actual Access Cost for the	Total cost		98.496,63 €
Unit Cost=(A+B)/(Number of Accesses *Number of samples per Access) [4]			€ 205,20
<p>[1] Maintenance is calculated as 8% of the total cost of the equipment (VAT excluded). For the NOA/TNA covered by this call, the equipment is considered to be in use 90% of the total usage time.</p> <p>[2] Costs related to the use of the Compute platform for storage. The calculation is EUR 3 per terabyte per month, i.e., EUR 36 per year/terabyte.</p> <p>[3] Indirect costs for providing access to the installation equal to 25% of the direct costs (Costs of consumables specifically used for the service access)</p> <p>[4] Unit Cost = Annual Total Cost [Direct Costs + Indirect Costs] / (Number of Accesses * Number of samples per access). The Unit Cost may vary depending on the service agreement signed by the parties and the technical report provided by the service manager. The maximum number of samples per access for this service is 24, and the unit cost may vary in relation to the sample saturation rate of the access.</p>			

Unit Access Cost for the services offered under National Open Access (NOA)

Implementing Entity	CNR-IBIOM		
Service Provided	MTP1		
Service Manager			
Number of accesses per year	2.000		
Instrumentation usage rate	90%		
Data storage volume (Tb)	6,000		
Cost of the instrumentations used to provide the service (IVA excluded)	638.791,00 €		
A. Direct eligible costs of providing access to the selected user groups, excluding personnel costs	costs of consumables and supplies specifically incurred for the provision of access to the selected users, in particular for carrying out their research work		Cost/year
	A1 - Consumables specifically used for service delivery (VAT excluded)		10.000,00 €
	A2 - Maintenance cost of all equipment used for service delivery [1]		45.992,95 €
	A3 - Storage costs [2]		216,00 €
	VAT		12.365,97 €
	Total direct costs per year		68.574,92 €
B. Indirect eligible costs: 25% cost of consumables			Costo/anno
	B1- overhead costs [3]		2.500,00 €
	Total indirect costs per year		2.500,00 €
Actual Access Cost for the	Total cost		71.074,92 €
Unit Cost=A+B/Number of			€ 35,54

[1] Maintenance is calculated as 8% of the total cost of the equipment (VAT excluded). For the NOA/TNA covered by this call, the equipment is considered to be in use 90% of the total usage time.

[2] Costs related to the use of the Compute platform for storage. The calculation is EUR 3 per terabyte per month, i.e., EUR 36 per year/terabyte.

[3] Indirect costs for providing access to the installation equal to 25% of the direct costs (Costs of consumables specifically used for the service access)

[4] Unit Cost = Annual Total Cost [Direct Costs + Indirect Costs] / Number of Accesses. The Unit Cost may vary depending on the service agreement signed by the parties and the technical report provided by the service manager.

Unit Access Cost for the services offered under National Open Access (NOA)

Implementing Entity	CNR-IBIOM		
Service Provided	MUP1		
Service Manager			
Number of accesses per year		1.200	
Instrumentation usage rate		90%	
Data storage volume (Tb)		12,00	
Cost of the instrumentations used to provide the service (IVA excluded)		638.791,00 €	
A. Direct eligible costs of providing access to the selected user groups, excluding personnel costs	costs of consumables and supplies specifically incurred for the provision of access to the selected users, in particular for carrying out their research work		Cost/year
	A1 - Consumables specifically used for service delivery (VAT excluded)		15.000,00 €
	A2 - Maintenance cost of all equipment used for service delivery [1]		45.992,95 €
	A3 - Storage costs [2]		432,00 €
	VAT		13.513,49 €
	Total direct costs per year		74.938,44 €
B. Indirect eligible costs: 25% cost of consumables			Costo/anno
	B1- overhead costs [3]		3.750,00 €
	Total indirect costs per year		3.750,00 €
Actual Access Cost for the	Total cost		78.688,44 €
Unit Cost=A+B/Number of		€ 65,57	

[1] Maintenance is calculated as 8% of the total cost of the equipment (VAT excluded). For the NOA/TNA covered by this call, the equipment is considered to be in use 90% of the total usage time.

[2] Costs related to the use of the Compute platform for storage. The calculation is EUR 3 per terabyte per month, i.e., EUR 36 per year/terabyte.

[3] Indirect costs for providing access to the installation equal to 25% of the direct costs (Costs of consumables specifically used for the service access)

[4] Unit Cost = Annual Total Cost [Direct Costs + Indirect Costs] / Number of Accesses. The Unit Cost may vary depending on the service agreement signed by the parties and the technical report provided by the service manager.

Actual Unit Access Cost for the access offered under National Open Access (NOA)

Implementing Entity	University of Bari		
Service Provided	WGS30-1, Whole Genome Sequencing on NovaseqX Plus, 64 samples		
Service Manager	Anna Maria D'Erchia		
Number of accesses per year	20		
Instrumentation usage rate	90%		
Data storage volume (Tb)	3,20		
Cost of the instrumentations used to provide the service (IVA excluded)	940.497,00 €		
A. Direct eligible costs of providing access to the selected user groups, excluding personnel costs	costs of consumables and supplies specifically incurred for the provision of access to the selected users, in particular for carrying out their research work		Cost/year
	A1 - Consumables specifically used for service delivery (VAT excluded)	27.377,79 €	547.555,80 €
	A2 - Maintenance cost of all equipment used for service delivery [1]		
	A3 - Storage costs [2]		115,20 €
	VAT		120.487,62 €
	Total direct costs per year		668.158,62 €
B. Indirect eligible costs: 25% cost of consumables			Costo/anno
	B1- overhead costs [3]		136.888,95 €
	Total indirect costs per year		136.888,95 €
Actual Access Cost for	Total cost		805.047,57 €
Unit Cost=(A+B)/(Number of Accesses *Number of samples per Access) [4]			€ 628,94
<p>[1] Maintenance is calculated as 8% of the total cost of the equipment (VAT excluded). For the NOA/TNA covered by this call, the equipment is considered to be in use 90% of the total usage time.</p> <p>[2] Costs related to the use of the Compute platform for storage. The calculation is EUR 3 per terabyte per month, i.e., EUR 36 per year/terabyte.</p> <p>[3] Indirect costs for providing access to the installation equal to 25% of the direct costs (Costs of consumables specifically used for the service access)</p> <p>[4] Unit Cost = Annual Total Cost [Direct Costs + Indirect Costs] / (Number of Accesses * Number of samples per access). The Unit Cost may vary depending on the service agreement signed by the parties and the technical report provided by the service manager. The maximum number of samples per access for this service is 24, and the unit cost may vary in relation to the sample saturation rate of the access.</p>			

Actual Unit Access Cost for the access offered under National Open Access (NOA)

Implementing Entity	University of Bari		
Service Provided	METV2.0 - Human Methylome profiling on iScan (Infinium MethylationEPIC v2.0) 24 samples		
Service Manager	Anna Maria D'Erchia		
Number of accesses per year		10	
Instrumentation usage rate		90%	
Data storage volume (Tb)		1,00	
Cost of the instrumentations used to provide the service (IVA excluded)		264.189,30	
A. Direct eligible costs of providing access to the selected user groups, excluding personnel costs	costs of consumables and supplies specifically incurred for the provision of access to the selected users, in particular for carrying out their research work		Cost/year
	A1 - Consumables specifically used for service delivery (VAT excluded)	9.701,24 €	97.012,41 €
	A2 - Maintenance cost of all equipment used for service delivery [1]		
	A3 - Storage costs [2]		36,00 €
	VAT		21.350,65 €
	Total direct costs per year		118.399,06 €
B. Indirect eligible costs: 25% cost of consumables			Costo/anno
	B1- overhead costs [3]		24.253,10 €
	Total indirect costs per year		24.253,10 €
Actual Access Cost for the access offered under the project = A + B	Total cost		142.652,16 €
Unit Cost=(A+B)/(Number of Accesses *Number of samples per Access) [4]			€ 594,38

[1] Maintenance is calculated as 8% of the total cost of the equipment (VAT excluded). For the NOA/TNA covered by this call, the equipment is considered to be in use 90% of the total usage time.

[2] Costs related to the use of the Compute platform for storage. The calculation is EUR 3 per terabyte per month, i.e., EUR 36 per year/terabyte.

[3] Indirect costs for providing access to the installation equal to 25% of the direct costs (Costs of consumables specifically used for the service access)

[4] Unit Cost = Annual Total Cost [Direct Costs + Indirect Costs] / (Number of Accesses * Number of samples per access). The Unit Cost may vary depending on the service agreement signed by the parties and the technical report provided by the service manager. The maximum number of samples per access for this service is 24, and the unit cost may vary in relation to the sample saturation rate of the access.

Unit Access Cost for the services offered under National Open Access (NOA)

Implementing Entity	UNIBA		
Service Provided	ONTDNWGS		
Service Manager	Anna Maria D'Erchia		
Number of accesses per year	40		
Instrumentation usage rate	90%		
Data storage volume (Tb) per access	60,00		
Cost of the instrumentations used to provide the service (IVA excluded)	400.000,00 €		
A. Direct eligible costs of providing access to the selected user groups, excluding personnel costs	costs of consumables and supplies specifically incurred for the provision of access to the selected users, in particular for carrying out their research work		Cost/year
	A1 - Consumables specifically used for service delivery (VAT excluded)	52.800,00 €	2.112.000,00 €
	A2 - Maintenance cost of all equipment used for service delivery [1]		
	A3 - Storage costs [2]		2.160,00 €
	VAT		465.115,20 €
	Total direct costs per year		2.579.275,20 €
B. Indirect eligible costs: 25% cost of consumables			Costo/anno
	B1- overhead costs [3]		528.000,00 €
	Total indirect costs per year		528.000,00 €
Actual Access Cost for the access offered under the project = A + B	Total cost		3.107.275,20 €
Unit Cost= (A+B)/(Number of Accesses* Number of samples per Access) [4]			€ 3.236,75

[1] Maintenance is calculated as 8% of the total cost of the equipment (VAT excluded). For the NOA/TNA covered by this call, the equipment is considered to be in use 90% of the total usage time. [1] Maintenance is calculated as 8% of the total cost of the equipment (VAT excluded). For the NOA/TNA covered by this call, the equipment is considered to be in use 90% of the total usage time. Maintenance costs should not be applied in the case they have been charged on the ELIXIRxNextGenIT project.

[2] Costs related to the use of the Compute platform for storage. The calculation is EUR 3 per terabyte per month, i.e., EUR 36 per year/terabyte.

[3] Indirect costs for providing access to the installation equal to 25% of the direct costs (Costs of consumables specifically used for the service access)

[4] Unit Cost = Annual Total Cost [Direct Costs + Indirect Costs] / [Number of Accesses * Number of samples per Access]. The Unit Cost may vary depending on the service agreement signed by the parties and the technical report provided by the service manager. The maximum number of samples per access for this service is 24, and the unit cost may vary in relation to the sample saturation rate of the access.

Unit Access Cost for the services offered under National Open Access (NOA)

Implementing Entity	UNIBA		
Service Provided	ONTHSWGS30		
Service Manager	Anna Maria D'Erchia		
Number of accesses per year	40		
Instrumentation usage rate	90		
Data storage volume (Tb) per access	60,00		
Cost of the instrumentations used to provide the service (IVA excluded)	400.000,00 €		
A. Direct eligible costs of providing access to the selected user groups, excluding personnel costs	costs of consumables and supplies specifically incurred for the provision of access to the selected users, in particular for carrying out their research work		Cost/year
	A1 - Consumables specifically used for service delivery (VAT excluded)	40.800,00 €	1.632.000,00 €
	A2 - Maintenance cost of all equipment used for service delivery [1]		
	A3 - Storage costs [2]		2.160,00 €
	VAT		359.515,20 €
	Total direct costs per year		1.993.675,20 €
B. Indirect eligible costs: 25% cost of consumables			Costo/anno
	B1- overhead costs [3]		408.000,00 €
	Total indirect costs per year		408.000,00 €
Actual Access Cost for the access offered under the project = A + B	Total cost		2.401.675,20 €
Unit Cost= (A+B)/(Number of Accesses* Number of samples per Access) [4]			€ 2.501,75

[1] Maintenance is calculated as 8% of the total cost of the equipment (VAT excluded). For the NOA/TNA covered by this call, the equipment is considered to be in use 90% of the total usage time. [1] Maintenance is calculated as 8% of the total cost of the equipment (VAT excluded). For the NOA/TNA covered by this call, the equipment is considered to be in use 90% of the total usage time. Maintenance costs should not be applied in the case they have been charged on the ELIXIRxNextGenIT project.

[2] Costs related to the use of the Compute platform for storage. The calculation is EUR 3 per terabyte per month, i.e., EUR 36 per year/terabyte.

[3] Indirect costs for providing access to the installation equal to 25% of the direct costs (Costs of consumables specifically used for the service access)

[4] Unit Cost = Annual Total Cost [Direct Costs + Indirect Costs] / [Number of Accesses * Number of samples per Access]. The Unit Cost may vary depending on the service agreement signed by the parties and the technical report provided by the service manager. The maximum number of samples per access for this service is 24, and the unit cost may vary in relation to the sample saturation rate of the access.

Unit Access Cost for ELIXIRxNextGenIT

Implementing Entity	IBSBC-CNR		
Service Provided	MUP2-MTP2-MLP1		
Service Manager	Daniela Gaglio		
Number of accesses per year		515	
Instrumentation usage rate		92%	
Data storage volume (Tb) per access		3,00	
Cost of the instrumentations used to provide the service (IVA excluded)		650.000,00 €	
A. Direct eligible costs of providing access to the selected user groups, excluding personnel costs	costs of consumables and supplies specifically incurred for the provision of access to the selected users, in particular for carrying out their research work		Cost/year
	A1 - Consumables specifically used for service delivery (VAT excluded)		35.500,00 €
	A2 - Maintenance cost of all equipment used for service delivery [1]		47.840,00 €
	A3 - Storage costs [2]		108,00 €
	VAT		18.358,56 €
	Total direct costs per year		101.806,56 €
B. Indirect eligible costs: 25% cost of consumables			Costo/anno
	B1- overhead costs [3]		8.875,00 €
	Total indirect costs per year		8.875,00 €
Actual Access Cost for the	Total cost		110.681,56 €
Unit Cost= (A+B)/(Number of Accesses* Number of samples per Access) [4]			€ 214,92
<p>[1] Maintenance is calculated as 8% of the total cost of the equipment (VAT excluded). For the NOA/TNA covered by this call, the equipment is considered to be in use 90% of the total usage time. Maintenance costs should not be applied in the case they have been charged on the ELIXIRxNextGenIT project.</p> <p>[2] Costs related to the use of the Compute platform for storage. The calculation is EUR 3 per terabyte per month, i.e., EUR 36 per year/terabyte.</p> <p>[3] Indirect costs for providing access to the installation equal to 25% of the direct costs (Costs of consumables specifically used for the service access)</p> <p>[4] Unit Cost = Annual Total Cost [Direct Costs + Indirect Costs] / [Number of Accesses * Number of samples per Access]. The Unit Cost may vary depending on the service agreement signed by the parties and the technical report provided by the service manager. The maximum number of samples per access for this service is xx, and the unit cost may vary in relation to the sample saturation rate of the access.</p>			